

Inkjet printing of ceramic precursors based on sol-gel media

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ABSTRACT

This work focuses on direct inkjet printing of sol-gel-based precursors using commercially available and low-cost inkjet printer to print complex features with high spatial resolution. It allows to prototype fine structures like waveguides, biosensors or gas sensors [1]. This work demonstrates a new method of modifying the consumer inkjet printer to prepare ceramic layers on fused silica substrate. We re-engineered the printer by modifying the hardware, while preserving the printer's ability to be controlled by conventional software. The hardware upgrade enables fluid deposition on rigid substrates with the print accuracy and precision close to unmodified printer using thermal ink cartridges [2]. Although this method of printing promises high processing speeds, the performance of this process is often limited by the rheological parameters of the ink [3]. In our study, we focus on ceramic precursors prepared by various sol-gel routes [4]. One of the significant issues in printing is premature clogging of inkjet printheads when printing aqueous sols [5]. To avoid clogging on internal surfaces of the printhead a systematic design of inkjet inks is needed. The design must address ink rheology, colloidal stability and suppress cracks formation during firing. Water based inks with low viscosity and moderate surface tension were designed. The rheological properties of the ink have been determined by viscosity, surface tension and contact angle measurements. Proper control over rheology and surface tension resulted in good printability [6]. The quality of printed patterns like line stability, edge acuity and cross-section of the lines was characterized by using confocal optical microscopy. Drying of the precursor yields composite powders forming mullite structure after firing at 1300°C, as confirmed by X-ray powder diffraction before realizing the inkjet printing. Proper adjustment of quantities of each component and processing conditions resulted in preparation of stoichiometric $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$ mullite layer in one step process.

Keywords: Ceramic coatings, Design of the ink, Inkjet printing, Mullite, Re-engineering of the printer, Sol-gel

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